

Thermal Decomposition and Kinetics of Dehydration of Praseodymium(III) Tartarate Hexahydrate

R. M. SHARMA and M. L. KAUL*

Department of Chemistry, University of Jammu, Jammu-180 004

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Praseodymium tartarate hexahydrate has been prepared and characterised on the basis of its elemental analysis ir and reflectance studies. The compound decomposes in four well-marked steps involving dehydration followed by partial and then complete conversion into carbonate and yielding oxide as the end-product.

The kinetics of dehydration step has been studied by non-isothermal method. The TG data has been analysed for the evaluation of various kinetic parameters by the application of integral, approximation and differential methods. The dehydration process proceeds by random nucleation mechanism.

RECENTLY some interesting studies have been reported on the thermal decomposition of rare earth tartarates¹. In continuation to our earlier work², we report the results of thermal decomposition of praseodymium tartarate hexahydrate.

Experimental

$\text{Pr}_2\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_{12}\text{O}_{18}\cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ was prepared by the reported method². The percentage of the metal was determined gravimetrically by precipitating it as $\text{Pr}(\text{OH})_3$ and weighing as Pr_2O_3 . Carbon and hydrogen were estimated by microanalytical method.

Simultaneous TG and DTG curves of the compound were recorded on a Mettler TA-3000 instrument in static air at a heating rate of 10 K min^{-1} , with sample weight, 6.976 mg; plot-length, 10 cm; and F.S. range, 10 mg as scan parameters.

The weight-loss at different temperatures and the total weight loss in the decomposition step was directly obtained from the TG curve and hence the fractional weight loss (α) at various temperatures was computed. From these values the α -T plot was drawn.

Ir spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Shimadzu IR-435 spectrophotometer. Reflectance spectra of the samples of the compound pre-heated to desired temperatures as indicated by TG curve were recorded on Beckmann-DK-2A spectrophotometer, keeping the concentration same in every case, using MgO as reference material and speed, 36 nm min^{-1} ; scale, 10 nm cm^{-1} ; sensitivity, 50.

An ECIL TDC-316 computer (India) was used to evaluate the kinetic parameters like energy of activation, pre-exponential factor, entropy of activation, apparent order of reaction and the mechanism involved in the dehydration process by the integral

method using Coats-Redfern³ and Piloyan-Ryabchikov-Novikova⁴ equations, the approximation method applying Horowitz-Metzger⁵ equation and the differential method using Freeman-Carroll⁶ equation by non-isothermal method.

Results and Discussion

Elemental analyses data reveal that the compound contains Pr, 33.75; C, 16.96; H, 2.80. $\text{Pr}_2\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_{12}\text{O}_{18}\cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires: Pr, 33.79; C, 17.27; H, 2.88%.

The ir spectrum of the compound shows a strong and broad band at 3380 cm^{-1} due to OH stretching vibrations of water and secondary alcoholic groups. The broadness of the band indicates the presence of intramolecular hydrogen bonding in the compound. The $\nu_{\text{as}}(\text{OCO})$ and $\nu_{\text{s}}(\text{OCO})$ bands appear at 1585 and 1375 cm^{-1} respectively. The doublet at 1110 cm^{-1} suggests that both the C-OH groups are coordinated dissimilarly^{2,7}. It suggests that tartarate ion is coordinated to Pr^{III} ion through two carboxylate groups and a hydroxy group, and the other secondary alcoholic group is coordinated to a neighbouring Pr^{III} ion. The splitting of C-OH stretching band appears due to the difference in the coordination of OH group in the chelate ring and that of OH group with the neighbouring Pr^{III} ion.

The TG and DTG curves of the compound are shown in Fig. 1. The thermal decomposition of the compound occurs in four steps. The first step of decomposition of the compound starts at 320 K and is marked with a regular loss in weight upto 465 K . The observed weight-loss of 13.21% (calcd. loss, 12.96%) at the end of this step corresponds to the elimination of six molecules of water, leading to the formation of anhydrous salt, $\text{Pr}_2\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_{12}\text{O}_{12}$.

The temperature of maximum rate of dehydration in this step is 363 K. The TG curve remains almost horizontal from 465 to 505 K, showing the stability of the anhydrous species within this range of temperature.

Fig. 1. TG and DTG curves; sample wt. = 6,976 mg.

The second step of decomposition starts beyond 505 K and continues upto 641 K. The observed weight-loss in this step, 29.0% (calcd. loss, 28.8%) suggests its partial conversion into carbonate giving the intermediate $\text{Pr}_4(\text{C}_4\text{H}_4\text{O}_6)_3(\text{CO}_3)_3$.

The third step of decomposition starts beyond 650 K and proceeds upto 710 K. The weight-loss of 44.90% (calcd. loss, 44.61%) in this step corresponds to the formation of praseodymium carbonate, $\text{Pr}_2(\text{CO}_3)_3$, which shows stability upto 725 K. The ultimate decomposition step starts beyond 725 K and extends upto 975 K. The observed weight-loss of 60.48% (calcd. loss, 60.45%) at this temperature corresponds to the formation of praseodymium oxide, Pr_2O_3 as the end-product, which remains stable beyond 975 K.

The complete thermal decomposition scheme of the compound may be represented as follows,

725–975 K

On heating the compound to 470 K, its dehydrated product retains all the principal bands in the ir spectrum of the original compound, except the band at 3380 cm^{-1} which undergoes a pronounced decrease in intensity, indicating the removal of water molecules at this temperature.

Fig. 2 shows the reflectance spectra of the compound at room temperature (303 K) and its samples preheated to the desired temperatures viz. 373, 423, 463 and 498 K. A marked variation in the intensity of the bands near 590, 485, 470 and 445 nm is observed with the progressive rise in temperature. The bands almost vanish at 498 K, suggesting the formation of a different product (anhydrous salt) at this temperature.

Fig. 2. Reflectance spectra at different temperatures: (I) 303, (II) 373, (III) 423, (IV) 463 and (V) 498 K.

Kinetics of decomposition: Fig. 3 presents the α vs T curve for the first decomposition step (dehydration) of the compound. The curve does not begin with apparent induction period and thus

Fig. 3. α - T curve for dehydration step.

suggests that the initial stages involve very little or no physical desorption and also indicates that no surface nucleation or branching occurs before the decomposition starts⁹. The beginning of α - T curve with acceleratory period, followed by a region of maximum rate which virtually continues upto the end of process ($\alpha=1$), is suggestive of there being no significant retention or decay period.

The kinetics of first decomposition step has been studied by non-isothermal method using the following equation.

(i) Coats and Redfern equation³ :

$$(a) \log \frac{g(\alpha)}{T^2} = \log \left[\frac{-\ln(1-\alpha)}{T^2} \right] = \frac{-E}{2.303 RT} + \log \left[\frac{ZR}{\beta E} \left(1 - \frac{2RT}{E} \right) \right] \text{ for } n=1 \quad (1)$$

$$(b) \log \frac{g(\alpha)}{T^2} = \log \left[\frac{1 - (1-\alpha)^{1-n}}{T^2} \right] = \frac{E}{2.303 RT} + \log \left[\frac{ZR}{\beta E} \left(1 - \frac{2RT}{E} \right) \right] \text{ for } n \neq 1$$

(ii) Piloyan-Ryabchikov-Novikova equation⁴ :

$$\log \frac{g(\alpha)}{T^2} = \log \frac{\alpha}{T^2} = \log \frac{ZR}{\beta E} - \frac{E}{2.303 RT} \quad (\alpha=0.05-0.5) \quad (2)$$

(iii) Horowitz and Metzger equation⁵ :

$$(a) \log g(\alpha) = \log [-\ln(1-\alpha)] = \frac{E \theta}{2.303 RT_m^2} \text{ for } n=1$$

$$(b) \log g(\alpha) = \log \left[\frac{1 - (1-\alpha)^{1-n}}{1-n} \right] = \frac{E \theta}{2.303 RT_m^2} \text{ for } n \neq 1 \quad (3)$$

(iv) Freeman and Carroll equation⁶ :

$$\frac{\Delta \log (d\alpha/dt)}{\Delta \log (1-\alpha)} = n - \frac{E}{2.303 R} \times \frac{\Delta(1/T)}{\Delta \log (1-\alpha)} \quad (4)$$

where T is temperature, R the molar gas constant, E the energy of activation, n the apparent order of reaction, T_m the peak temperature, $\theta = (T - T_m)$, Z the pre-exponential factor, β the rate of heating,

and $g(\alpha) = \int_0^\alpha \frac{d\alpha}{f(\alpha)}$, where $f(\alpha)$ is the appropriate

function of α depending upon the mechanism involved. The $g(\alpha)$ values corresponding to different models were computerised and the values of $g(\alpha)/T^2$ vs $1/T$ plotted for equations (1) and (2). The linear fits for different models were investigated. The best-fit linear plot with minimum least-square error was selected while applying Coats-Redfern equation. The values of slope, intercept, E and Z were calculated from this plot as also in the case of Piloyan-Ryabchikov-Novikova plot and the mechanism was decided. The value of entropy of activation (ΔS^*) was computed from equation (5).

$$Z = \frac{kT_m}{h} \exp \left(\frac{\Delta S^*}{R} \right) \quad (5)$$

where k is the Boltzmann constant and h the Planck constant. Plots of $g(\alpha)$ vs θ were constructed applying equation (3) and the best-fit linear plot having minimum least-square error was selected to find $g(\alpha)$ and hence the mechanism.

The E value was calculated from the slope of this plot and Z was determined from equation (6).

$$Z = \frac{E}{RT_m^2} \beta \exp \left(\frac{E}{RT_m} \right) \quad (6)$$

The value ΔS^* was calculated from equation (5) used earlier for the purpose.

In case of Freeman and Carroll method, the left-hand-side of equation (4) was plotted against $\Delta(1/T)/\Delta \log(1-\alpha)$ and E was obtained from the slope and n from the Y -intercept.

It is observed that best-fit linear plot in the case of Coats-Redfern and Horowitz-Metzger methods is obtained for $g(\alpha) = -\ln(1-\alpha)$, which suggests that the dehydration step follows the rate equation, $d\alpha/dt \propto (1-\alpha)^n$. Thus mechanism involved in this step is 'random nucleation'⁹ with apparent order reaction (n)=1.

The values of E , Z and ΔS^* obtained by Coats-Redfern method are 34.85 kJ mol⁻¹, 2.4×10^8 s⁻¹ and -200.95 JK⁻¹ mol⁻¹, while those by Horowitz-Metzger method are 35.92 kJ mol⁻¹, 7.9×10^8 s⁻¹ and -191.00 JK⁻¹ mol⁻¹. Piloyan-Ryabchikov-Novikova method gives E , Z and ΔS^* as 42.38 kJ mol⁻¹, 5.5×10^8 s⁻¹ and -174.89 JK⁻¹ mol⁻¹ respectively. The value of E obtained by Freeman-Carroll method is 22.63 kJ mol⁻¹ and that of $n=1$. The values of kinetic parameters obtained are reasonable and in fair agreement. It must, however, be mentioned that these values of kinetic parameters are for a single sample size and a single heating rate of 10 K min⁻¹, that being the rate most commonly used for such work. The value of energy of activation and other parameters can be different for different heating rates and sample sizes.

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References

1. M. L. KAUL, K. K. RAINA and P. N. KOTRU, *J. Pure Appl. Phys.*, 1987, 25, 224; *J. Mater. Sci.*, 1986, 21, 3933; A. G. GLATZ, I. LITANT and B. RUBIN in "Analytical Calorimetry", eds. R. S. POTER and J. F. JOHNSON, Plenum, New York, 1970, Vol. 2, p. 225.
2. R. M. SHARMA and M. L. KAUL, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1987, 64, 459; *J. Therm. Anal.*, 1989, 35, 2143.
3. A. W. COATS and J. P. REDFERN, *Nature (London)*, 1984, 68, 201.
4. G. O. PILOYAN, I. D. RYABCHIKOV and I. S. NOVIKOVA, *Nature (London)*, 1966, 212, 1229.
5. H. HOROWITZ and G. METZGER, *Anal. Chem.*, 1964, 35, 1464.
6. E. S. FREEMAN and B. CARROLL, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1958, 62, 394.
7. K. C. SATPATHY and P. HERNA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1981, 58, 1002.
8. D. A. YOUNG in "The International Encyclopaedia of Physical Chemistry, Solid and Surface Kinetics", ed. F. C. TOMPKINS, Pergamon, London, 1966, p. 68.
9. K. R. MAMPAL, *Z. Phys. Chem.*, 1940, 187, 43, 235.